

Link to PROSPERO Registration:

PROSPERO [CRD42022335848](https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/display_record.php?ID=CRD42022335848)

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Appendix 1

medic* wast* **OR** unwanted medic* **OR** unwanted pharm* **OR** unwanted drug* **OR** unused medic* **OR** unused pharm* **OR** unused drug* **OR** drug wast* **OR** pharm* wast* **OR** prescription* wast* **OR** unnecessary medic* **OR** unnecessary drug* **OR** unnecessary pharm* **OR** extra medic* **OR** extra drug* **OR** extra pharm* **OR** surplus medic* **OR** surplus drug* **OR** surplus pharm* **OR** untouched medic* **OR** untouched drug* **OR** untouched pharm* **OR** remaining medic* **OR** remaining drug* **OR** remaining pharm* **OR** returned medic* **OR** returned drug* **OR** returned pharm*

COMBINED with

- (1) patient* **OR** pharmacist* **OR** doctor* **OR** prescriber* **OR** student*
- (2) perception* **OR** opinion* **OR** belief* **OR** awareness* **OR** attitude* **OR** concept* **OR** knowledge*
- (3) solution* **OR** reduc*
- (4) medic* appropriate* **OR** medic* manage* **OR** appropriate* **OR** medic* review* **OR** drug review*